

THE EFFECT OF LONG PERIOD HEAT-TREATMENT ON CARBON
FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

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Summary

The change of the tensile strength of the C/Al composite wires and the content of the aluminum carbide in the interfaces have been studied. The authors note that the strength of composite wires was damaged after long period heat-treatment at 495°C and was damaged remarkably above 540°C. Also, the content of the aluminum carbide increases with increasing the temperature and the time of treatment.

Introduction

A number of investigations have been reported about the effect of long period heat-treatment on the mechanical property of C/Al composites. In order to keep up the strength of materials, temperature and time are very important parameters in the designing process.

Harrigan [1] showed that the strength of the Gr/Al composites was not damaged after heat-treatment at 465°C for 1000 hr. Akimilsu Okur [2] studied the heat-treatment of C/Al composites in air and indicated that the strength did not damage at 350°C for 100 hr. Khan [3] reported that the chemical reaction between aluminum and graphite began at about 500°C and the degression of the tensile strength occurred, he suggested that the reaction process was diffusion-controlled.

The results are different because of the difference of the fibers and the matrix as well as the method of the fabrication. The authors have studied the change of the C/Al composite wires after heat-treatment at 450°C for 100 hr. The results show that the tensile strength of the C/Al composite wires and the content of the aluminum carbide do not change obviously. Therefore, it is necessary to study the change of the material property and the content of the aluminum carbide in higher temperature.

In present paper we will discuss the effect of the long period heat-treatment on the C/Al composite wires about strength and the content of the aluminum carbide at 495°C and even above this temperature.

Experimental Procedure

The carbon fiber-aluminum composite wires used in this investigation are fabricated in our laboratory, by means of the method of chemical vapour deposition to form Ti-B coating and then infiltrate the melt of pure aluminum into the carbon fibers. The volume fraction of carbon fibers in wires are 50% approximately. The specimens are treated at 495°C, 540°C, 580°C respectively in an Ar atmosphere go on for 100 hr. and sampling in every 20 hr. After that, the tensile strength and the content of the aluminum carbide (Al_4C_3) for each heat treated sample are determined with the mechanical testing machine as well as the gas chromatograph analysis respectively. Besides, the fracture surface of these samples are observed with the scanning electron microscope.

Results and Discussion

Tensile Strength:

The tensile strength of as-received carbon aluminum composite wires and heat treated wires at different temperatures and times are shown in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

Table 1. The tensile strength after heat-treatment at difference temperature and time

Temp. (°C)	Time (hr.)	0	0.5	2	10	20	40	60	80	100
495	b*	92.1	95.8	89.5	77.2	76.8	68.8	65.7	72.1	70.7
	n*		-4	3	16	17	25	29	22	23
540	b*	82.5	65.6	55.5	51.8	50.9	46.3	45.9	49.6	49.7
	n*		21	33	37	38	44	44	40	40
580	b*	74.1	--	--	--	31.7	28.8	31.3	28.4	24.9
	n*		--	--	--	58	61	58	62	66

b*: tensile strength (Kg/mm²)

n*: tensile strength degratation rate (%)

It is evident that the tensile strength of these wires have been affected by heat-treatment if the temperature is higher than 495°C, since the strength of wires decreases with increasing the temperature. But it does not damage at 450°C for 100 hr. as the dash line in Fig. 1. this phenomenon confirm the suggestion of Harrigan, that the composition of the interface between the fiber and the matrix remained unchanged at 465°C for 1000 hr. Fig. 1. also shows that the strength degrade dramactically when the treatment time exceed τ_c and does not degrade after the time τ'_c . The value of τ_c and τ'_c depend on the treatment temperature.

Fig. 1. Relation between strength and heat-treatment temperature and time.

Fig. 2. Relation between the content of the Al₄C₃ and the heat-treatment time.

Aluminum Carbide:

The chemical reaction between carbon fiber and matrix occurs at high temperature. The reaction product was Al_4C_3 identified by the method of the gas chromatograph analysis and X-ray diffraction analysis. The degree of the reaction and the content of the aluminum carbide in the interface region relate to the treatment temperature and time. The relations between the content of the Al_4C_3 and treatment time at different temperature are shown in Fig. 2.

Obviously, the content of the aluminum carbide changes slightly at $450^\circ C$, but increase dramatically at the first stage of heat-treatment period if the temperature is higher than $450^\circ C$, and then becomes slow progressively. Fig. 3 and Fig. 4 represent the development of the chemical reaction in the interface is a function against temperature T^a and time τ^b (where $a > 1$ and $0 < b < 1$). These results show that the reaction process is diffusion controlled. The carbon diffuses into aluminum is impeded gradually because the brittle layer of the Al_4C_3 forms and covers the surface of the fibers completely, so that this layer may block the diffusion process. It conforms with the data of the tensile strength in Fig. 1.

Fig. 3. Relation between the content of the Al_4C_3 and the time $\tau^{1/2}$.

Fig. 4. Relation between the content of the Al_4C_3 and the temperature.

Fracture Surface:

The microstructure of the fiber surface before and after heat-treatment at $540^\circ C$ for 60 hr. and at $580^\circ C$ for 40 hr. is illustrated in Fig. 5 respectively. The specimens are prepared by dissolving the Al matrix just prior to SEM examination. As presents in Fig. 5(a) the surface is flat and smooth for the case of before heat treatment. However, interface reaction at $540^\circ C$ for 60 hr. lead to coarsening the surface as shown in Fig. 5(b), and the surface becomes more serious damage at $580^\circ C$ for 40hr. as shown in Fig. 5(c).

(a) (X5000)

(b) (X5000)

(c) (X5000)

Fig. 5. Illustrate the micro-structure of the fiber surface (a) before heat treatment (b) after heat treatment at 540°C for 60 hr. (c) and at 580°C for 40 hr.

Fig. 6(c) illustrates the microstructure of the fracture surface longitudinal specimen after heat-treatment at 580°C for 20 hr. The chemical reaction in the interface region can be clearly observed. Fig. 6(a) and Fig. 6(b) shows the fracture surface before and after heat-treatment at 540°C for 80 hr. Only slight difference can be distinguished. It is also shown that a distinct change in the interface region with variation of temperature, but only small change with the time carries on.

(a) (X3000)

(b) (X3000)

(c) (X3000)

Fig. 6. Illustrate the microstructure of the fracture surface of the longitudinal specimen:
(a) before heat treatment
(b) after heat treatment at 540°C for 80 hr.
(c) and at 580°C for 20 hr.

Conclusions

The following conclusions can be deduced from this investigation:

(1) The tensile strength of the C/Al composite wires is not affected by heat-treatment at 450°C for 100 hr. and damaged distinctly at or above 495°C.

(2) The decrease of the strength is affected mainly by the heat-treatment temperature but slightly by the time.

(3) Chemical reaction occurs at the C/Al interface region to form aluminum carbide, and lead to decrease the strength of the composites. The reaction rate increases with increasing the temperature in the beginning and then becomes slow progressively when the brittle layer of the Al_4C_3 is formed and covers the surface of the fibers completely.

References

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